

Sequencing, Mutation and Evolution of SMC Proteins: An Overview

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Introduction

- SMC stands for Structural Maintenance of Chromosomes, these proteins represent a large family of ATPases that participate in various aspects of higher-order chromosome organization and dynamics (Losada & Hirano, 2005).
- In 1993, the first SMC protein was characterized as a gene product required for proper chromosome segregation in yeast. Same year, using different approaches, a number of related proteins were identified in different organisms, laying the foundation of the SMC superfamily.
- These proteins are large polypeptides, each spanning 1000–1500 amino acids. They form dimers in which two antiparallel coiled-coil arms are connected by a flexible hinge and the distal end of each arm constitutes an ATP-binding domain.
- Both the archaeal and bacterial genomes, contain only one SMC gene, six distinct SMC paralogues, which are found in individual eukaryotes, each of the eukaryotic SMC has a specific dimer partner- SMC1–3, SMC2–4 and SMC5–6.
- Each SMC dimer forms a functional complex with a distinct set of non-SMC subunits like, SMC1–3 forms the core of the cohesin complex that functions in sister chromatid cohesion, SMC2–4 forms part of the condensin complex, a key player in mitotic chromosome condensation. Bacterial SMC is involved in chromosome partitioning and that is thought to be an ancestor of condensin and cohesin. The SMC5–6 complex is implicated in DNA repair and checkpoint responses during processes (Hirano, 2000).

Figure 1. The architecture of cohesin and condensin, two representative SMC protein complexes in eukaryotes.

Classification

1. Eukaryotic SMCs-

- Eukaryotes have at least six SMC proteins in individual organisms and they form three distinct heterodimers with specialized functions like;
 - A pair of SMC1 and SMC3 acts as core subunits of the cohesin complexes involved in sister chromatid cohesion.
 - Likewise, a pair of SMC2 and SMC4 acts as the core of the condensin complexes implicated in chromosome condensation.
 - A dimer composed of SMC5 and SMC6 acts as part of a yet-to-be-named complex implicated in DNA repair and checkpoint responses (Losada *et al.*, 1998).

2. Prokaryotic SMCs-

- SMC proteins are conserved from bacteria to humans.
- All most bacteria have a single SMC protein in individual species that forms homodimer.
- In a subclass of Gram -ve bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, a distantly related protein which is known as MukB, that plays an equivalent role as of SMCs (Hirano *et al.*, 1997).

Structure of SMC proteins

1. Primary Structure-

- These proteins are 1,000 - 1,500 amino acid long (chained). This protein has a modular structure that is composed of the following domains;
 - Walker ATP-binding motif
 - Coiled - coil region I
 - Hinge region
 - Coiled - coil region II
 - Walker B ATP-binding motif; signature motif

2. Secondary structure-

- This is comprised when SMC dimers form a V - shaped molecule with two long coiled-coil arms.
- To make such a unique structure, SMC protomer is self - folded through anti - parallel coiled - coil interactions, which at end forms a rod - shaped molecule.
- At one end of the molecule, the N - terminal and C - terminal domains jointly forms an ATP binding domain, The other end is called a hinge domain. Two protomers then dimerize through their hinge domains and assemble a V - shaped dimer.
- The length of the coiled-coil arms is ~50 nm long, this such a long "antiparallel" coiled - coils are very rare, and found only among SMC proteins (and its relatives such as Rad50).
- The ATP - binding domain of SMC proteins is structurally related to that of ABC transporters, which are large family of transmembrane proteins that actively transport small molecules across cell membranes (Hirano, 2001).

Gene organization and evolutionary history

- Eukaryotes have at least six genes encoding structural maintenance of chromosomes (SMC) proteins, which are conserved from yeast to mammals; in other cases, additional genes have been identified with either tissue - specific patterns of expression or additional functions (Losada and Hirano, 2001).
- These SMC genes were first identified in genetic screens in the budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Cobbe and Heck, 2002).
- As their original name 'stability of minichromosomes' suggest, defect in SMC proteins destabilize chromosome segregation and hence SMC are in most cases essential for viability of organisms.

- SMC genes have been identified by biochemical approaches in vertebrates and by further genetic screenings in yeasts (*S. cerevisiae* and *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*), nematodes (*Caenorhabditis elegans*), insects (*Drosophila melanogaster*) and plants (*Arabidopsis thaliana*).
- Evolutionary conservation of SMC genes extends to prokaryotes; several species have a single gene, although there are two genes in *Bacillus subtilis* (encoding proteins that are 95% similar to each other) and a second potential SMC gene is found in *Aquifex aeolicus* (two encoded SMC proteins are only 20% similar to each other). Interestingly, *Escherichia coli* does not have a gene encoding a *bona fide* SMC protein, but it does have functionally conserved gene, *mukB* (Graumann, 2001).

References

- Losada A, Hirano T (2005). Dynamic molecular linkers of the genome: the first decade of SMC protein. *Genes Dev.* **19**(11):1269–1287.
- Hirano, T. (2000). Chromosome cohesion, condensation, and separation. *Annual review of biochemistry.* **69**(1):115-144.
- Losada A, Hirano M, Hirano T (1998). Identification of Xenopus SMC protein complexes required for sister chromatid cohesion. *Genes Dev.* **12**(13):1986–1997.
- Hirano T, Kobayashi R, Hirano M (1997). Condensins, chromosome condensation complex containing XCAP-C, XCAP-E and a Xenopus homolog of the Drosophila Barren protein. *Cell.* **89**(4):511–21.
- Graumann, P. L. (2001). SMC proteins in bacteria: condensation motors for chromosome segregation? *Biochimie.* **83**(1):53-59.
- Cobbe, N., & Heck, M. M. (2000). SMCs in the world of chromosome biology from prokaryotes to higher eukaryotes. *Journal of structural biology.* **129**(2-3):123-143.

